

CONTINUOUS PROCESS OF STRUCTURAL FRAMES FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The technical and economical resolution of the engineer and designer of a structure type frame or chassis, has created up to the present day, a real constructive problem that in our opinion hasn't been resolved in a convincing way.

Let's take the case of a truck's frame, as an example. This structural part is being produced nowadays, in the same way it was 70 years ago, by using the same technology consisting of two steel profiles and a serie of cross-pieces joined to the previous ones on the basis of metallic parts with their corresponding bolts.

It's the same technique used to produce window frames and door frames, loading platform, etc...

The technology consisting in manufacturing straight metallic profiles, joined together by means of quadrants, welding, bolts, etc..., is the basis of its difficulty and, high consequent cost, which is incurred when manufacturing bent metallic profiles.

The close relation between aspecific material and its manufacturing process comes to light once more.

Figure 1. View of a 3d continuous structure.

Description of the process

A fundamental characteristic of Composites is their flexibility in design and consequently the future potential of their shape. This is possible, to a great extent, due to the characteristics of the materials that are used and on the other hand, due to the variety of manufacturing systems available.

Regarding the materials and if we refer in particular to resin, this may come in a liquid state or in prepreg, that is to say, in completely manageable forms.

With regard to fibres, these are handled easily, be it in the forms of continuous fibres as in fabrics, mat, etc...

If we venture the various methods of manufacturing, these chassis may be obtained by the prepreg system over mould, filament winding, RTM, or handlay-up, using hybrid technologies or variants, according to the size, design of the part or serie to be manufactured.

Characteristics of manufactured parts.

First of all, let us start by saying that the part we have taken into consideration is U shaped and therefore open.

The profile may be rectangular, circular, elliptic or pear shape in form, but always and this is a particular characteristic, in a continuous way and with the profile wings facing inwards, looking at each other.

The continuity of the structure avoids break at 90° or 45° as has been the case with metallic structures, by removing, joints, solderings, bolts or reinforcement parts.

This means breaking with the traditional well known studied concept applied to the Ingeenering process to date.

The result of this technology apart from its cleaner and more precise line is that the structure will never break at the angles , simply because it is twice as resistant at those points.

In other words, the resistance of order has changed places and the point that was previously considered as weak (corner), is now the more resistant.

These characteristics do not end there. We may go on by reinforcing the straight sections, now in turn the weakest ones, by means of two processes:

- a) By inserting a further chassis in the inner part of the previous one, that is to say one inside the other, as seen with Russian dolls. In the particular case of the chassis of a Trailer cabin , up to 3 chassis, were placed one inside the other. We answered, with them, in a specific and optimized way, to the maximum effort concentrated which supposed the 5th wheel or King-Pin.
- b) Another possible variant is by simply closing the straight and open section, with a "U" shaped intersection in Composite material produced in a continuous way. This avoid the possibility of the wings opening at the same time strengthening the structure and other required, eliminating the torque working over the profil.

This evidently leads to a wide scope of possibilities which were unthinkable to date when using Composites in the structural field.

Industrial application

At first we had in mind to apply this type of chassis in Composite in the manufacturing process of structural elements subjected to various types of stress tests such as flexion-compression-traction, together with the most common suchs as environmental corrosion, very low thermic transmission and high resistance against damage together with the important weight saving factor.

From this point, emerged the first industrial aplications, both of them completely different from each other, both in size and their functional character.

Let us give you a brief description in order to explain in further detail the above mentioned:

- a) Chassis of trailer truck.

The largest chassis is 5,8 m long by 0,9 m wide and its U section measures 290 mm for some wing, of 120 mm in their maximum figure. It took inscribed other two chassis, one

medium of 4 m length and finally other smaller one of 1 m approximately; in both cases and because of being inscribed, the widths and sections in U, were inferior to their immediate superior.

Naturally, the most important point in the truck was its weight, achieving a saving close to 40% with respect to the steel.

Other important factor was the total absence of corrosion, the muffling of noise and even, the absorption of impact energy, as the module of the resultant material, on being inferior to the steel one, absorbs bigger quantity of impact energy, shaped like a deformation.

b) Cages for storage and transportation of butane gas containers. Here the requirements are quite different. Evidently, we started from some sections in U extremely small, of 50 x 25 mm, and we had to work the design with enormous care, so as to achieve an acceptable rigid assembly.

It was required that the Composite absorb the impact of the steel bottles weighing, up to 30 Kg., when full, without bringing about deformation in the structure. This phenomenon causes very serious problems in those made of steel, causing stoppages, haults and financial losses in the automatic filling line.

For us, this was the most challenging problem because the chassis were very small and the margin of tolerance was considerably reduced

Besides these achievements, we feel that the following parts can be made perfectly using this structure:

- Loading platforms.
- Towing lines for road vehicle
- Chassis for coach and passenger cars.
- Telescopic structures for high tension electric transportation.
- Radar towers, lighthouses and telecommunication antennas.
- Structures or bus cases, chair lifts and elevators.
- Platforms for mussel-beds and marine crops of young fish.
- Refrigerator containers and isotherm, fixed and mobile.
- Containers for aeronautical catering,
- Setting frames for changeable transportation cistern to set over trailer.

Our intention is not to give an endless list but simply to point out the primary factors which make this structure highly versatile.

Summary

We wouldn't like to omit a question that we consider extremely important: the joints of the frames among them, to form cage like tridimensional structure.

If at first such joints were produced by the opening of windows, nowadays, they may be solved very cleanly, by fitting the frames inside a union profile, also made in Composite.

The solution is really clean, sure, fast and constitutes an absolute novelty in the structural framework.

In any of these cases, window or profile, the frames may be joined by adhesive or structural rivets, specifically thought and developed for Composites, such as FYBRFAST and FYBRDRIVE, of proved effectiveness, manufactured by the French Firm A.H.G.

To sum up, we would like to assert that the technology of the manufacturing of chassis or structural elements in continuous produced in COMPOSITE as we have pointed out here, admits these materials, be it through their own weight into the restricted and exclusive structural field.

Never before, has an Engineer, Designer or Technician generally speaking, had so much liberty and possibilities in choosing materials, resistant characteristics and industrial design.

Only the analysis and indepth knowledge of these fascinating materials and their processes of production, will enable us to obtain the most from these materials and exploit their potential to the full.

Figure 2. Detail of a corner.

Figure 3. Test of the whole structure.

Figure 4. Test of a frame.